

Simulation and Performance Analysis of Three Phase PV Array Inverter

Md. Mashrur Islam, Shahriar Ahmed

Abstract— The requirement for a cleaner domain and the nonstop increment in power requests makes sustainable power source generation like sun based and twist progressively intriguing. Vitality generation utilizing solar vitality could be an answer for the regularly expanding force requests. This interest over-burdens the dissemination frameworks just as the power stations negatively affecting force quality and accessibility. One answer for this issue is matrix associated photovoltaic (PV) frameworks. In this paper we are displaying a three stage photograph voltaic cell-based inverter framework utilizing MATLAB programming, which comprises of PV Array, network framework and sunlight-based inverter. The framework chips away at Solar power. The objective of this undertaking is to Simulate, structure, creates and examines the execution of PV based inverter framework. The inverter is IGBT connect based controlled framework. The framework is tried on resistive and inductive burden. Voltage/current waveform investigation, control quality and framework examination are done by utilizing power quality analyzer just as burden sharing between photovoltaic exhibit is finished. In this model the consonant pay of waveform is likewise presented. Finally, the control circuit, is talked about and planned in MATLAB/Simulink intelligent programming which results sinusoidal yield from the inverter.

Index Terms—3-Phase, PV Array, Inverter, Grid connected inverter, IGBT, MATLAB/Simulink.

I. INTRODUCTION

THIS persistently expanding vitality utilization over-burdens the conveyance frameworks just as the power stations, hence negatively affecting force accessibility, security and quality. One of the answers for beating this is the Distributed Generation (DG) frameworks [1-6]. DG frameworks utilizing sustainable power sources like sun oriented or wind have the favorable position that the power is delivered in nearness to where it is expended limiting the misfortune because of transmission lines. In the most recent decade sun-based vitality innovations have turned out to be more affordable and progressively productive, which have made it an alluring arrangement being cleaner and more earth inviting vitality asset than customary ones. All things

considered a PV framework is still significantly more costly than different strategies for vitality age given the high assembling expenses of PV boards [7]. One of the real focal points of PV innovation is that it has no moving parts in this way the equipment is vigorous; it has a long lifetime and low support prerequisites and above all it is one arrangement that offers ecologically neighborly power age. These days PV boards are available in regular daily existence: controlling wrist watches, little number crunchers, providing loads in remote locales and, and in particular, they are associated with the open framework, creating the green intensity of things to come [8-12]. The square graph is given underneath.

Fig. 1: Block diagram of PV system [13]

II. THEORY

The capacity to produce electrical power by methods for changing over sun powered light is called Photo voltaic. It initially was portrayed in 1839 by Becquerel when he watched two disparate materials would build up an electric potential when their intersections where enlightened with photons. Present day Photovoltaic (PV) cells utilize a semiconductor p-n intersection that in the wake of engrossing light vitality, results in an expanded populace of accuse bearers of a potential identified with the band hole and furthermore into cell warming which debases the execution [14-16]. An ordinary sun-oriented cell comprises of a 0.2mm thick monocrystalline or polycrystalline silicon wafer having two layers that present diverse electrical properties upgraded by doping with polluting influences making an electric field at the intersection region. At the point when daylight impacts the sun-oriented cell the vitality from the photons makes free charges that are isolated by the electrical field, making a potential so when a heap is put between the terminals a photograph flow (I_{pv}) is made. The most well-known material utilized in photocells today is silicon (Si) separated in monocrystalline, polycrystalline, and formless. The measure of vitality they can convey changes relying upon the material

Manuscript received December 14, 2018.

M. M. Islam is with the Dept. of EEE, Rajshahi University of Engineering & Technology, Rajshahi, Bangladesh. (corresponding author e-mail: mashrur.samit@gmail.com)

S. Ahmed, is with Ahsanullah University of Science & Technology, Dhaka, BD. He is now with the Department of EEE, AUST, Dhaka, BD.

Doi: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2667368>

of the cell and the occurrence of daylight. A straightforward PV cell from a displaying viewpoint is a perfect current source in parallel with a perfect diode as found in Figure 2.1 [17]. The two parameters used to show and describe a PV cell are: the open circuit voltage (Voc) and the short out current (Isc). The Voc is the greatest voltage which a sun powered cell can give at zero current. The Isc is the most extreme current which a sunlight-based cell can give at zero voltage. The yield current from the PV cell can be discovered utilizing the condition is:

$$I = I_{sc} - I_d \text{ (i)}$$

Where Isc is the short circuit current that is equal to the photon generated current and Id is the current shunted through the intrinsic diode.

Fig.2: Ideal PV cell.

The diode current is given by Shockley's diode equation:

$$I_d = I_0 * (e^{qV_d/kT} - 1) \text{ (ii)}$$

1. I₀ is the reverse saturation current of the diode
2. q is the electro charge valued at 1.602x10⁻²³ C
3. V_d is the diode's voltage
4. k is Boltzmann's constant valued at 1.381x10⁻²³ J/K
5. T is the junction temperature in Kelvin combining.

Equation (i) and Equation (ii) we then obtain:

$$I = I_{sc} - I_0 * (e^{qV/kT} - 1) \text{ (iii)}$$

All three configurations follow the same basic modeling equations. The simple PV cell model neglects to take into consideration a series of parameters [3, 17, 18] that create a more accurate model represented in Figure 2:

1. The series resistance (Rs): that accounts for any resistance in the current paths through the semiconductor material, the metal grid, contacts and currents controlling the system. This value also accounts for the loss associated with connecting a number of cells in series.
2. The parallel (shunt Rp) resistance: is a loss associated with a slight leakage current through a parallel resistive path to the device. In most models it is neglected because its effect isn't as noticeable unless a large number of cells are connected in parallel [19].
3. A recombination factor related directly to the depletion region of PV cells and to the number of cells connected in series. Usually it's represented by a second diode in the equivalent circuit, or characterized by a factor in the Equation (ii).

Fig.3: Precise circuitry of PV model.

Taking into account all the additional elements mentioned the Equation (iii) changes to:

$$I = I_{sc} - I_0 * (e^{q(V+I*Rs)/nkT} - 1) - \frac{(V+I*Rs)}{R_p} \text{ (iv)}$$

Where n also is sometimes described as a, being the ideality factor and its value is between 1 and 2 [4]. For the purposes of this research we have adopted the value proposed in [5] of 1.3. The equivalent final circuit of the PV module is in Figure (iii).

Fig.4: PV model equivalent circuitry.

The short circuit can be calculated at any given temperature using:

$$I_{sc,T} = I_{sc,Tref} * [1 + Ki - (T - Tref)] \text{ (v)}$$

Isc at the reference temperature is found on the datasheet, and a refers to the temperature coefficient of Isc in percent change per degree. Both measurements are done under the standard irradiance of 1000W/m². Normally the reference temperature is 25 Deg. C. The photon generated current also varies based on the irradiance (G) according to the following equation:

$$I_{sc,G} = I_{sc,Gref} * [G/Gref] \text{ (vi)}$$

Combining both equations and simplifying we then obtain a generic expression for the short circuit current. The assumption that Isc ≈ Ipv [20] is generally used since the series resistance is low and the parallel resistance is high, leading then to:

$$I_{pv} = (I_{sc} + Ki \Delta T) G/Gn \text{ (vii)}$$

The last term of Equation (iv) is I₀ that is dependent on temperature described by equation:

$$I_{0,T} = I_{0,Tref} * (T/Tref)^{3/n} * e^{-[\frac{qV}{nk} * (\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{Tref})]} \text{ (viii)}$$

III. THREE PHASE INVERTERS IN SIMULINK

Power Inverter is a device that converts a DC source into an AC source. Power inverters produce one of three different types of wave output: 1. Square Wave 2. Modified Square Wave or Modified Sine wave 3. Pure Sine Wave or True Sine Wave The three different wave signals represent three different qualities of power output. A three-phase inverter's topology was presented in Figure c.

Fig 9 (a) and (b) shows the results for output voltages. The magnitude is 448 and angle between them is -11.21 respectively. This output is taken from LC filter. The waveforms are some more variation. But after the AC Break and timer system the variation between waveforms become less as shown in Fig. 10 (a) & (b).

Fig.10: With AC break Output Voltage non-filtered (blue node), Filtered (red node) and the output current (green node).

V. CONCLUSION

This paper displayed a three-stage IGBT based Inverter, which utilizes single DC source and PV framework as DC source and associated with three stage network frameworks is utilized as a heap to watch the execution attributes of the inverter. Utilization of IGBT inverter lessens the expense of multiphase sun-oriented inverter significantly. By this topology, improve yield waveform from the framework. The benefit of this topology is an assistance to diminish the expense. MATLAB/SIMULINK programming enables us to display the framework associated photovoltaic (PV) framework which is valuable to comprehend and ace the execution of PV frameworks by upgrading the plan and bringing down the expenses by shortening the advancement cycles just as to improve the unwavering quality and effectiveness of the framework.

REFERENCES

- [1] Mallik, Avijit, Md Arman Arefin, Fazlur Rashid, and Md Asfaquzzaman. "Solar based plugged-in hybrid engine driven rickshaw (auto-rickshaw) & its feasibility analysis for Bangladesh." In *Proceedings of the international conference on mechanical, industrial and materials engineering RUET*. 2017.
- [2] Mallik, Avijit, and Arman Arefin. "Micro Hybridized Auto-rickshaw for Bangladesh: A Solution to Green Energy Vehicle." *The Open Mechanical Engineering Journal* 12, no. 1 (2018).
- [3] Arefin, Md Arman, Avijit Mallik, and Md Asfaquzzaman. "Renewable energy-assisted hybrid three-wheeler: A numerical investigation." *Advances in Mechanical Engineering* 10, no. 12 (2018): 1687814018814372.
- [4] Arefin, Md Arman, and Avijit Mallik. "Numerical investigation of solar and wind energy assisted plugged in hybridized engine driven auto-rickshaw/three-wheeler." *AIMS ENERGY* 6, no. 2 (2018): 358-375.
- [5] Chowdhury, Avijit, Bipul Biswas, and Biswanath Mallik. "Negative Differential Resistance and Photovoltaic Phenomena Observed in Nanostructured Organic Heterojunction." *Journal of nanoscience and nanotechnology* 13, no. 6 (2013): 4134-4140.
- [6] Mallik, Avijit, Shaik Asif Hossain, Asif Bin Karim, and Shahajada Mahmudul Hasan. "Development of LOCAL-IP based Environmental Condition Monitoring using Wireless Sensor Network." *International Journal of Sensors, Wireless Communications and Control* 9 (2019).
- [7] Avijit, Mallik, and Md Hasan. "PV/T Systems for Renewable Energy Storage: A Review." *World Scientific News* 96 (2018): 83-95.

- [8] Saha, Sabhasachi, Souvik Roy, Md Rahman, and Md Hasan. "Micro-hybrid with Ultra-Capacitor Based Three-Wheeler." *World Scientific News* 97 (2018): 69-79.
- [9] McAfee, Terry, Benjamin C. Hoffman, Xiao You, Joanna M. Atkin, Harald Ade, and Daniel B. Dougherty. "Morphological, Optical, and Electronic Consequences of Coexisting Crystal Orientations in β -Copper Phthalocyanine Thin Films." *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 120, no. 33 (2016): 18616-18621.
- [10] Fernando, M. G., and K. A. I. L. Wijewardena Gamalath. "Nonlinear optical properties of photonic crystals." *World Scientific News* 97 (2018): 1-27.
- [11] Gupta, Somu, and Avinash Pratap Singh. "Fuzzy Based Dual-Axis Solar Tracking Technique." *World Scientific News* 113 (2018): 138-147.
- [12] Habubi, Nadir F., and Abdulazeez O. Mousa. "Fabrication and characterization of ZnO/p-Si heterojunction solar cell." *World Scientific News* 18 (2015): 118-132.
- [13] Manokari, M., and Mahipal S. Shekhawat. "Biogenesis of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles using *Couroupita guianensis* Aubl. Extracts-A Green Approach." *World Scientific News* 29 (2016): 135-145.
- [14] Abd, Ahmed N., Mohammed O. Dawood, Majid H. Hassoni, and Ali A. Hussein. "Investigation on the structural, optical and topographical behavior of Cadmium oxide polycrystalline thin films using electrochemical depositing method at different times." *World Scientific News* 37 (2016): 249-264.
- [15] Kadhim, Raheem G., and Raheem Saleh Kzar Ban. "Effect of Cd Doping on Structural and Some Optical Studies of Nano CuO Films Prepared by Sol-Gel Technique." *World Scientific News* 64 (2017): 69-83.
- [16] Abdul-Ameer, Zehraa N., and Ibrahim R. Agool. "Studying structural and optical properties of ZnO-CdO nanocomposites." *World Scientific News* 23 (2015): 35-45.
- [17] Wilas, Janusz, Robert Maśniak, Piotr Daniszewski, and Paula Jadczyk. "Renewable energy sources today and tomorrow." *World Scientific News* 60 (2016): 103-112.
- [18] Stannowski, Bernd, Luana Mazzarella, Yen-Hung Lin, Simon Kirner, Anna B. Morales-Vilches, Lars Korte, Steve Albrecht et al. "Nanocrystalline silicon oxide interlayer in monolithic perovskite/silicon heterojunction tandem solar cells with total current density > 39 mA/cm²." In *2018 IEEE 7th World Conference on Photovoltaic Energy Conversion (WCPEC)(A Joint Conference of 45th IEEE PVSC, 28th PVSEC & 34th EU PVSEC)*, pp. 2627-2630. IEEE, 2018.
- [19] Ogedengbe, Emmanuel OB, Omokehinde Igbekoyi, Abideen Bakare, Olufemi J. Alonge, Manasseh B. Shitta, and Marc A. Rosen. "Flexibility of Organic Thermoelectric Material for Photovoltaic Solar Energy Management and Conversion." *The Open Fuels & Energy Science Journal* 11, no. 1 (2018).
- [20] Husain, Shagufta Bano, and Maruph Hasan. "Epitaxial Lattice Matching and the Growth Techniques of Compound Semiconductors for their Potential Photovoltaic Applications." *Journal of Modern Materials* 5, no. 1 (2018): 34-42.

Md. Mashrur Islam has been graduated from the Dept. of Electrical & Electronic Engineering, RUET, Rajshahi. He has deep research interest in PEC Antenna design, Graphene material and wireless communications. He is currently working as an Operations Engineer in NEPC Consortium Power Ltd. (A subsidiary of Pendekar Energy Ltd.). He has published some of his researches in international journals